

TAX PLANNING THROUGH MEDICAL EXPENSES: A STUDY OF EARNINGS MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIAN DEPOSIT BANKS

Dr. Chinedu Michael Okafor

Department of Accountancy, Paul University, Akwa

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17540515>

Abstract

This ascertained the effect between corporate tax shields of medical expenses and earnings management of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ex Post Facto research was adopted. Data were obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled banks. The study employed regression analysis via e-view 9.0. The study revealed that medical expenses is positively and significantly affect earnings management. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the bank management should increase their medical expenses in order to reduce their tax expenses, hence, tax shield is a benefit of debt financing over equity financing.

Keywords: Corporate tax shield, medical expenses and Earnings management

Introduction

The fact that the tax paid by a company is the transfer of wealth from the company to the shareholders causes shareholders to encourage the management to be more aggressive to the tax which could lead to tax shield practices (Paohan, 2019). Tax shield practices increases the wealth and cash flow of the company thereby leading to increase in the shareholders' wealth (Anne, Abdul, & Anis, 2016). It is the expectation of the shareholders that management's actions on their behalf will focus on income maximization. This includes the pursuit of all the opportunities to reduce tax liabilities at reduced cost. Tax shield is a reduction in taxable income of an individual or corporation by claiming allowable deductions, such as mortgage interest, medical expenses, charitable donations, amortization and depreciation. It refers to a deliberate but legally accepted way of attempting not to pay tax (Paohan, 2019). It is a form of tax planning by which individuals and corporate organizations minimize the amount they pay to the government each year by taking advantage of the loophole opportunities to reduce their tax (VanDenburgh, 2019). These deductions reduce the tax payer's taxable income for a given year or defer income to future years (Martani & Persada, 2019). Tax shield lowers the overall amount of taxes owed by individual tax payer or a business. Such deductions and deferment take place when earnings are created or managed or mismanaged by management.

Many studies have also been carried out on tax shield/tax avoidance and earnings management; many of these studies such as Amidu and Yorke (2017); Tarek (2017); Amidu, Kwakye, Harvey and Yorke (2016),

Aries (2015) and Harnovinsah and Lisya, (2014) found positive relationship with and significant effect on between tax avoidance, debt/leverage and firm's earnings management the other studies, significant effect was found between operating leverage and earnings management (EM) and the studies were associated with increased tax avoidance activities. The prior studies failed to acknowledge medical expenses as a measure of tax shield, hence capable of limiting the tax payable for the period. This has form the significant of the present study. In attempt to fill the gap, this study sought to assess the extent corporate tax shield on medical expenses has affected earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

The corporate tax shield strategy can be used to increase the value of a business, since it reduces the tax liability that would otherwise reduce the value of the entity's assets. The effects of the tax shield are used in cash flow analyses, since the amount of cash paid in taxes is impacted (Paohan, 2019). Tax shield strategies are available for both business and individual tax returns. A tax shield is a reduction in taxable income for an individual or corporation achieved through claiming allowable deductions such as mortgage interests, medical expenses, charity donations, amortization, and depreciation (Murray, 2019). These deductions reduce a taxpayer's taxable income for a given year or defer income taxes into future years (Paohan, 2019). One of the components of tax shield is interest expense which is a tax deductible expense. Therefore the tax shield (being a benefit of debt financing over equity financing) is an important factor that Tax shields according to Murray (2019) involved investments and purchases that are tax deductible. Some common examples include Deductions for medical expenses for individuals. If expenditures on medical expenses are greater than the standard deduction, the excess expenses are tax deductible. If you are considering major surgery, for example, you might want to look at whether you want the tax shield in one year or another, to lower your taxable income influence the company's capital structure choice (Valaskova & Bakes, 2018).

Medical Expenses

These refer to the costs incurred for medical and healthcare services, treatments, medication and equipment. They also include expenses paid for the prevention, diagnose and treatment of physical and mental health issues. Good examples which should be further described include doctor visits hospital stays surgeries, prescription drug's medical insurance premiums, and certain medical test in term of tax planning, corporation can use medical expenses as a tax shield through the following and more.

- Medical Expenses Deduction
- Health Insurance Reemums
- Health Savings Accounts
- Employee Wellness Programme

The health system is a complex mixed system with private hospitals operating in a free market and public hospitals operating in a government controlled capacity. The private health sector is responsible for about 60% of healthcare service delivery while the public health sector account for 40%.²⁹ The public health

sector is on the verge of collapse due to inefficiency, poor infrastructure and poor resources. Although the local, state and federal governments are responsible for primary, secondary, and tertiary levels of care respectively, there is poor coordination of healthcare services among the three levels of health system in Nigeria due to duplication of responsibilities. Primary healthcare (PHC) system which is expected to be the foundation of the country's health system has failed to provide basic healthcare services to the population due to problem of poor budgetary allocation, decaying and poor infrastructure, poor governance structure, poor service delivery and poor health worker performance.

Nie and Feng (2022) examined residents' high medical expense is the core challenge that needs to be solved urgently in China's medical reform for a long time. Based on the panel data of 30 provinces in Chinese Mainland during 2011–2019, we evaluate the impact of China's national comprehensive medical reform pilot policy on residents' medical expenses by using the difference-in-differences model. The results show that the pilot policy was generally conducive to reducing residents' medical expenses, resulting in a reduction of 2.13% in per capita medical expenses for inpatients, but the effect on per capita medical expenses for outpatients was insignificant. Mechanism analysis shows that hospital competition and institutional environment played a moderating role in the effect of the pilot policy on residents' medical expenses reduction. The more intense the hospital competition, the better the institutional environment, and the significant of the reduction effect. In addition, the reduction effect of the pilot policy was greater in the central provinces, the provinces with poor medical infrastructure, and the provinces with strong financial strength.

The empirical accounting research has commonly relied on various proxies to measure earnings management. Here, the aggregate accruals approach has been the dominant strategy. This approach relies on the fact that accounting earnings consist of cash flows (actual cash receipts and payments) and accruals (accounts receivable and depreciation). The latter component is influenced by business operations but also by certain managerial decisions and subjective assessments of different assets and liabilities, which can be a breeding ground for earnings management (Sundvik, 2017).

Earnings management

According to Scott (2012), earnings management is a management action to choose the accounting policy of a certain standard to manage profit. Earnings management is the management intervention in the financial reporting process in order to give benefit to managers. In addition, Belkaoui (2006) defined earnings management as an ability to manipulate the available options and to make the appropriate choices in order to achieve the expected profit. It is accomplished through managerial discretion over accounting choices and operating cash flow

(Ofurum, Okoye, & Ezejiofor, 2021). The underlying assumption in preparing Financial Statements is that Managers exercise discretion to manage the book income upward without increasing the taxable income (Mills & Newberry, 2001).

Discretionary Accrual (DA), which is an accrual component chosen by managers as policy in preparing financial statement, can be used to detect the existence of earnings management in a company. Sanjaya (2011) mentioned that the high or positive discretionary accrual measurement result indicates the income increasing done by the manager. On the contrary, the low or negative discretionary accrual measurement result indicates the income decreasing done by the manager. If the discretionary accrual measurement result is zero, then the manager does not perform earnings management.

Earnings management which includes

- a. Income smoothing: manipulation of revenue and expenses to create a more consistent earnings)
- b. Cookie Jar Reserves: setting aside reserves during good financial years to create a cookie jar which can be used to boost earnings in future year of underperformance.
- c. Big Bath Accounting: taking large write offs or recognition high levels of expenses to decrease earnings. This enables them to reset their financial and create a balance for future improvement.
- d. Create Revenue Recognition: Recognizing revenue before they are truly earned or delay the recognition of revenue/expenses.
- e. Shifting Expenses: Shifting expenses from one period to another through various methods e.g. delay recognition of improperly capitalize expense/assets.
- f. Regulatory Arbitrage: Exploratory loopholes or gaps in accounting standards regulation to manipulate their earnings. Other examples include: aggressive perpetration of accounting rules or structure complex transaction to achieve desired results.

Methodology

Due to the nature of the study, *ex-post facto* research design was adopted for the study. The researcher does not have direct control of the independent variables because their manifestation have already occurred or manipulated. This design is considered appropriate because the study aims at measuring the relationship between one variable and another in which the variables cannot be manipulated, hence the adoption of the design.

The population of the study consists of deposit money banks on the Nigeria Exchange Group from 2012-2024. The researchers used purposive sampling technique to select five quoted deposit money banks (Access bank, Fidelity bank, GTB, First banks and FCMB) on the Nigeria Exchange Group out of the twenty one banks stated as population of this study. The choice of these banks was based on the availability of data that covered the period under study.

To obtain reliable information that helped in this study to ensure the effectiveness of the study in question, data were collected from only secondary sources. The data were extracted from the annual reports and audited accounts of the banks under study from 2012 to 2024.

Model Specification

The model for this study was adapted from the study of Ofurum, Okoye, and Ezejiofor (2021) which was modified to suit the variables under study. The adapted model is presented as thus: $EAMGT = f(MDE, CHD, AMT, DEP)$.

Thereafter the newly modified model of this study is presented in functional form as stated below.

$$EMG = f(MDE, LIQ) \dots \dots \dots i$$

The econometric form of the model is stated in the equation below.

$$EMG_{it} = \beta_1 MDE_{it} + \beta_3 LIQ_{it} + \sum_{it} \dots \dots \dots ii$$

Where:

EMG = Earnings Management (represents by TAC = Total accrual period)

MDE = Medical Expenses LIQ = Firm liquidity β_1 = Constant/Intercepts β_1 = Regression Coefficient

\sum = Error Term i = Cross section

t = Time Period

Measuring Dependent Variable (Earnings Management)

This study used the modified Jones’s model (Dechow et al., 1995) to measure the level of earnings management or discretionary accruals (DTAC). This model used total accruals (TAC) that are classified as discretionary components (DTAC) and non-discretionary components (NDTAC). Thus, defined as follows:

$$TAC = NDTAC + DTAC$$

Where:

TAC = Total accrual period t

NDTAC = Value of non-discretionary accruals

DTAC = Discretionary accrual

Method of Data Analysis

In order to investigate corporate tax shield and earnings management, the study used descriptive statistics, correlation and simple regression analysis. Other diagnostic tests were also conducted out, test like Johansen cointegration rank test and pairwise granger causality test.

Decision rule:

The study’s hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance. In view of that, when the pstatistics is less than 0.05, the null hypotheses is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. But when the P-statistics is higher than the critical level of 0.05, the null hypotheses is not rejected.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were analyzed with the help of E-view 9.0. The results are presented in the relevant tables.

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics provides evidence on the mean distribution, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, median and the count of the data collected which span from 2012 to 2024.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	TAC	MDE	LIQ
Mean	-4.39E+08	415307.3	14.68540
Median	-9.63E+08	403634.0	0.245427
Maximum	4.14E+09	603891.0	90.61944
Minimum	-5.50E+09	252258.0	0.091010
Std. Dev.	2.65E+09	97433.30	28.46337
Skewness	-0.007685	0.266396	1.716583
Kurtosis	2.352170	2.260947	4.526614
Jarque-Bera	1.137284	2.248102	38.23401
Probability	0.566294	0.324961	0.000000
Sum	-2.86E+10	26994975	954.5508
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.51E+20	6.08E+11	51850.47
Observations	65	65	65

Source: E-view 9 Output

From table 1 above, the result revealed the mean of total accrual period (TAC) was -4.390, with maximum value of 4.140 and minimum value of -5.500. The standard deviation stood at 2.650. The medical expenses (MDE) value over the period was 415307.3; the maximum value was 603891.0 while the minimum stood at 252258.0. The standard deviation was 97433.30. Firm liquidity average was valued at 14.685 with maximum and minimum values of 90.619 and 0.091 respectively. From table 1 above, the Jarque-Bera (JB) which test for normality or the existence of outlier or extreme values among the variables indicates that

our variables are normally distributed and significant at 5% level and the result could be generalized. This also implies that a least square regression can be employed to calculate the regression models.

Test of Hypothesis

In order to scrutinize the effect of TAC on the variable (MDE and LIQ) and to also test the formulated hypotheses, regression analysis was employed. The regression results are presented and discussed in Table 2 below.

H₀₁: Corporate Tax Shield has no significant influence on earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 2: Regression analysis between TAC, MDE and LIQ

Dependent Variable: TAC

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 07/06/25 Time: 23:36

Sample: 2012 2024

Periods included: 13

Cross-sections included: 5

~~Total panel (balanced) observations: 65~~

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1.03E+10	1.18E+09	-8.722418	0.0000
MDE	26380.49	3018.094	8.740778	0.0000
LIQ	-74660744	10331273	-7.226674	0.0000

-

R-squared	0.564570	Mean dependent var	4.39E+08	Adjusted R-squared	0.550524	S.D. dependent var	2.65E+09
S.E. of regression	1.78E+09	Akaike info criterion	45.48240				
Sum squared resid	1.96E+20	Schwarz criterion	45.58275				
Log likelihood	-1475.178	Hannan-Quinn criter.	45.52200				
F-statistic	40.19401	Durbin-Watson stat	1.158744				
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000						

In Table 2, the regression analysis revealed that medical expenses (MDE) and firm liquidity (LIQ) has a positive and significant effect on earnings management. From the findings in the Table 2, the value of adjusted R squared was 0.55. This implies that only 55% changes in earnings management of banks could be accounted for by independent variable, MDE and control variable, LIQ, while 45% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 1.159 advocates that the model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 40.19401 and the associated F-statistical probability is equal to 0.000, so the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected.

The probability of the slope coefficients indicates that; P-value = 0.000 < 0.05. The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1 = 26380.49$; $t = 8.741$ for TAC implies that medical expenses are positively related to earnings management, and also statistically significant at 5%.

Decision

Since the P-value of 0.000 is less than the critical value of 5% (0.05), then, it would be upheld that medical expenses have a positive and significant effect on earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria at 5% level of significance, thus, H_0 is preferred to H_1 .

Discussion and Conclusion

This ascertained the effect between corporate tax shield of medical expenses and earnings management of five selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. In this study, data were obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the selected banks. The hypothesis was tested with regression analysis, from the findings, it revealed that probability of the slope coefficients indicates that; P-value = 0.000 < 0.05). The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1 = 26380.49$; $t = 8.740778$ for TAC implies that medical expenses is positively related to earnings management, and also statistically significant at 5%. The result from the findings is in congruence with Prabowo, Winarna, Aryani, Falikhatun and Gantiyowati (2020); Ayunku and Uzochukwu (2020). This implies that the increase in tax shield on medical expenses will also result on the increase in earnings management of the corporation. Conclusively, the tax shield of medical expenses has a positive and significant effect on earnings management of Nigerian banks. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the bank management should increase their medical expenses in order to reduce their tax expenses, hence, tax shield is a benefit of debt financing over equity financing.

REFERENCES

- Abdurahman, A., Awad, S. H., Erik, V. N., & Jeffrey, S. R. (2003). Indicator variables model of firm's size-profitability relationship of electrical contractors using financial and economic data. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 129(2), 192–197.
- Abubakar, S. J., & Oladele, J. O. (2018). Firm size and audit quality on earnings management of quoted oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 6(12), 28–38.
- Adegbite, T. (2015). The analysis of the effect of corporate income tax (CIT) on revenue profile in Nigeria. *American Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, 1(4), 312–319.
- Agrawal, G. P., Swain, A. K., & Bhuyan, A. K. (2017). Corporate debt restructuring in scheduled commercial banks in India: An analysis. *International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah*, 5(2), 92–112.
- Aguolu, O. (2000). *Taxation and tax management in Nigeria*. Enugu: Meridian Associates.
- Alareeni, B. (2018). The impact of firm-specific characteristics on earnings management: Evidence from GCC countries. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 10(2), 85–104. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMFA.2018.10012808>
- Alawiye-Adams, A. A., & Afolabi, B. (2013). Nigeria deposit money banks' credit administration and the incidence of bad loans: An empirical investigation. SSRN. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2329589> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2329589>
- Albertazzi, U., & Gembacorta, L. (2006). Bank profitability and business cycle. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 5(4), 393–409.
- Allingham, M. G., & Sandmo, A. (1972). Income tax evasion: A theoretical analysis. *Journal of Public Economics*, 1(3), 323–338.
- Al-Saedi, A. A. (2018). Earnings management and its relationship with stock returns: An empirical study on a sample of Qatari listed industrial companies. *Academy of Accounting and Finance Journal*, 22(5), 1–13.
- Alton, R. G., & Hazen, J. H. (2001). As economy flounders, do we see a rise in problem loans? *Journal of Accounting Research*, 5(3), 20–34.

Alves, S. (2012). Ownership structure and earnings management: Evidence from Portugal. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 6(1), 57–74.

Amidu, M., & Yorke, S. M. (2017). Tax avoidance and earnings management of firms in Ghana: Does the funding strategy matter? *International Journal of Critical Accounting*, 9(3), 238–264. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJCA.2017.088740>

Amidu, M., Yorke, S. M., & Harvey, S. (2016). The effects of financial reporting standards on tax avoidance and earnings quality: A case of an emerging economy. *Journal of Accounting & Finance*, 16(2), 129–150.

Anjum, H., Saif, M. I., Malik, Q. A., & Hassan, S. (2012). Earnings management and firms' profitability: Evidence from Pakistan. *European Journal of Economics, Finance & Administrative Sciences*, 47, 13–18.

Amidu, M., Kwakye, T. O., Harvey, S., & Yorke, S. M. (2016). Do firms manage earnings and avoid tax for corporate social responsibility? *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 8(2), 158–171.

Amiram, D., Bozanic, Z., & Rouen, E. (2015). Financial statement errors: Evidence from the distributional properties of financial statement numbers. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 20(4), 1540–1593.

Anokye, S. A., & Okri, J. A. (2015). Staff development practices, attitude to work and work performance among academic staff in tertiary institutions in Ghana. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 20(10), 41–44.

Appah, E. (2004). *Principles and practice of Nigeria taxation*. Port Harcourt: Ezevin Mint Printers and Publishers.

Aprilla, K. D. K., Rohman, A., Chariri, A., & Ghozali, I. (2016). Credit risk and earning management mediate the relationship between cash compensation and cash performance: Evidence from Indonesia. *The Social Sciences*, 11(21), 5060–5070.

Ardison, K. L. M., Martinez, A. L., & Galdi, F. C. (2012). The effect of leverage on earnings management in Brazil. *Advances in Scientific and Applied Accounting*, 5(3), 305–324.

Aries, V. (2015). The influence of leverage and its size on the earnings management. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(8), 413–425.

- Armstrong, C., Blouin, J., & Larcker, D. (2012). The incentives for tax planning. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 53, 391–411.
- Atu, O. G., Uniamikogbo, E., & Atu, O. O. K. (2018). Firm attribute and tax aggressiveness in the Nigeria banking sector. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development*, 17(1), 161–178.
- Atu, O. O., Atu, F. O., Enegebe, O. P., & Atu, E. C. (2016). Determinants of earnings management in Nigeria quoted companies. *Igbinedion University Journal of Accounting*, 1, 118–133.
- Ayunku, P. E., & Uzochukwu, A. (2020). Credit management and issues of bad debts: An empirical study of listed deposit banks in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 14(3), 32–49.
- Aza, I. E. (2018). Influence of firm size on financial performance of deposit money banks quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 4(9), 297–302.
- Azeem, K., Khan, B., Warraich, F. A., Khadim, I., Zahoor, N., & Ashraf, Z. (2017). Reasons and effects of non-performing loans in the banking industry of Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(4), 41–49.
- Babalola, Y. A. (2013). The effect of firm size on firms' profitability in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(5), 90–94.
- Ball, R. (1989). *Accounting, auditing and the nature of the firm*. W.E. Simon Graduate School of Business Administration, University of Rochester.
- Banks and other financial institutions decree. (2004). *The laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria: Banks and other financial institutions decree 25, 1991, ACT, CAP, B.L.F.N 2004*.
- Barus, I. S. L., Sarumpaet, T. L., Edison, A., Maisyarah, R., & Pulungan, E. (2019). Relationship between leverage and firm size toward real earning management (Unit analysis of mining company Indonesia exchange stock). *Journal of Reviews on Global Economics*, 8, 672–687.
- Bartov, E., Gul, F. A., & Tsui, J. S. (2019). Discretionary-accruals models and audit qualifications. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 30(3), 421–452.
- Beatty, A., & Weber, J. (2003). The effects of debt contracting on voluntary accounting method changes. *The Accounting Review*, 78(1), 119–142.

- Beck, T., & Laeven, L. (2008). Resolution of failed banks by deposit insurers: Cross-country evidence. In A. Demirgüç-Kunt, E. Kane, & L. Laeven (Eds.), *Deposit insurance around the world: Issues of design and implementation* (pp. 14–21). MIT Press.
- Belkaoui, A. R. (2006). *Accounting theory* (5th ed.). Jakarta: Interpreters and Ali Akbar YuliantoRisnawati, Salemba Four.
- Beneish, M. D. (1999). The detecting of earnings manipulation. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 55, 24–26.
- Berger, A., & DeYoung, R. (1997). Problems and cost efficiency in commercial banks. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 21, 849–870.
- Bexley, J. B., & Nenninger, S. (2012). Financial institutions and the economy. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(1), 20–22.
- Bhundia, A. (2012). A comparative study between free cash flows and earnings management. *Business Intelligence Journal*, 5(1), 123–129.
- Biswas, R., Marchese, C., & Privileggi, F. (2013). Firm's tax evasion in a principal-agent model with self-protection. *Journal of Economics*, 110(2), 125–140.
- Blessing, N. N. (2020). Tax shield and earnings management in Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management*, 2(12), 798-808.
- Boudriga, A., Taktak, N. B., & Jellouli, S. (2009). Banking supervision and nonperforming loans: A cross-country analysis. *Journal of Financial Economic Policy*, 1(4), 286-318.
- Bozanic, Z., Hoopes, J. L., Thornock, J. R., & Williams, B. M. (2017). IRS attention. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 55(1), 79-114.
- Buijink, W., Janssen, B., & Schols, Y. (1999). Corporate effective tax rates in the European Union. *De Economist*, 153(1), 47-66.
- Caminal, R., & Xavier, V. (2004). Price dynamics and consumer learning. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*, 8(1), 95-131.

Caprio, G., & Klingebiel, D. (2002). Bank insolvency: Bad luck, bad policy or bad banking. In Annual World Bank Conference on Development Economics. Washington, DC: The World Bank.

Central Bank of Nigeria. (2010). Prudential guidelines for deposit money banks in Nigeria. *The Billion*, 4(2), 20-31.

Chen, K. P., & Chu, C. C. (2005). Internal control versus external manipulation: A model of corporate income tax evasion. *RAND Journal of Economics*, 36(1), 151-164.

Chen, S., Chen, X., Cheng, Q., & Shevlin, T. (2010). Are family firms more tax aggressive than non-family firms? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 95(1), 41-61.

Christensen, J., & Murphy, R. (2020). The social irresponsibility of corporate tax avoidance. *Development*, 7(3), 37-44.

Clemente-Almendros, J. A., & Sogorb-Mira, F. (2018). Costs of debt, tax benefits and a new measure of non-debt tax shields: Examining debt conservatism in Spanish listed firms. *Spanish Accounting Review*, 21(2), 162-175.

Crocker, K. J., & Slemrod, J. (2005). Corporate tax evasion with agency costs. *Journal of Public Economics*, 89(9), 1593-1610.

Crutchley, C. E., & Hansen, R. S. (1989). A test of the agency theory of managerial ownership, corporate leverage, and corporate dividends. *Financial Management*, 18(4), 36-46.

Cudia, C. P., & Dela Cruz, A. L. C. (2018). Determinants of earnings management choice among publicly listed industrial firms in the Philippines. *DLSU Business & Economic Review*, 27(2), 119-129.

Davidson, W. N., Jiraporn, P., Kim, Y. S., & Nemec, C. (2004). Earnings management following duality-creating successions: Ethnostatistics, impression management, and agency theory. *Academy of Management Journal*, 47(2), 267-275.

DeAngelo, H., & Masulis, R. W. (1980). Leverage and dividend irrelevancy under corporate and personal taxation. *The Journal of Finance*, 35(2), 453-464.

DeAngelo, H., & Masulis, R. W. (1980). Optimal capital structure under corporate and personal taxation. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 8, 3-29.

Dechow, P., Sloan, R., & Sweeney, A. (1995). Detecting earnings management. *The Accounting Review*, 70(2), 193-225.

Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Huizinga, H. (1999). Determinants of commercial banks' interest margin and profitability: Some international evidence. *World Bank Economic Review*, 13(2), 329-408.

Desai, M. A. (2005). The degradation of reported corporate profits. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 19(4), 171-192.

Desai, M. A., & Dharmapala, D. (2008). Tax and corporate governance: An economic approach. In *Tax and Corporate Governance* (pp. 13-30).

Desai, M. A., & Dharmapala, D. (2018). Corporate tax avoidance and firm value. *American Law and Economics Association Annual Meetings*, 27.

Desai, M. A., & Dharmapala, D. (2019). Earnings management, corporate tax shelters, and book-tax alignment. *National Tax Journal*, 62(1), 169-186.